

Psychological Aspects of Learning Motivation of Students

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Abstract:

In this article, Russian and foreign psychologists have researched the problem of motive and motivation, the psychological aspects of students' educational motivation, and the opinions and views on the components of educational motivation. Also, the opinions about the factors affecting the motivation of the individual are stated.

Keywords: motive, motivation, learning motivation, theoretical-instinctual approach, theoretical-personal approach, theoretical-associative approach, value factor, emotional factor, social factor, self-regulation factor, informational factor, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation.

Enter. Today, in the science of pedagogical psychology, the problem of learning motivation is recognized as one of the most important problems. Educational motivation is considered as the main factor of successful achievement of the main goals of educational activities. In practice, the construction of the system of educational activities and the educational process in accordance with uniform organizational templates is not sufficiently focused on the individual psychological characteristics of the student, the relationship between the form of education and internal factors as an external factor is rarely taken into account. After all, the factor that determines the student's activity and develops his activity is educational (learning) motivation.

Many reforms implemented in the national education system show that any changes in the socio-economic and political situation in the country, changes in social relations, always based on the new needs of society, revise the goals and tasks of pedagogical activity. requires a rib.

At the same time, urgent questions arise: in what direction is it possible to influence the motivational field of students? What factors affect learning motivation?

After all, today the goals of education are changing - from acquiring knowledge to personal development, mastering self-development technologies. Also, improving the ability to make non-standard decisions in problematic situations, forming personal directions, creative approach to learning, self-development and personal growth is becoming a requirement and task of today. In this regard, the problem of motivation to increase the effectiveness of educational activities, which is rightfully considered one of the main issues in pedagogical psychology, is becoming more urgent.

Literature analysis and methodology. Theoretical and methodological issues of the influence of the form of education on learning motivation from Russian psychologists A. A. Andreev, A. A. Akhayan, G. N. Butyrin, E. V. Vlasov, V. G. Domrachev, V. M. Danilchenko, V. E. Kadochkina, M. P. Karpenko, A. A. Kashaev, V. G. Kinelev, O. A. Lavrov, S. L. Lobachev, M. I. Nejurina, O. P. Okolelov, E. S. Polat, V. I. Soldatkin, I. V. Tikhomirova, A. V. Khutorskaya) and foreign psychologists R. Delling, J. Daniel, D. Keegan, M. Moore, O. Peter, studied by B. Holmberg.

Study motivation of students, as well as from Russian psychologists A. A. Verbitsky, T. I. Evmenova, N. V. Kuzmina, P. Platonov, L. B. Yushkova, V. A. Yakunin and other scientists were studied.

In the holistic concept of the structure and genesis of the motivation of educational activity developed by E. V. Karpova, it is clearly defined that the leading mechanism of the genesis of the motivational sphere of the individual in the educational activity is the mechanism of interlevel interaction of "neighboring" levels. In the process of mastering educational activities, the general pattern of the genesis of the individual's motivational sphere is that it obeys all the main principles of system genesis - unevenness, heterochrony, integration and differentiation strengthening, consolidation. In the process of mastering educational activities, the general pattern of the genesis of the individual's motivational sphere is that it obeys all the main principles of system genesis - unevenness, heterochrony, integration and differentiation strengthening, consolidation. All these laws and principles are most clearly manifested not at the individual level, but at the level of the main motivational subsystems.

In the process of mastering educational activities, it was found that the genesis of the motivational field has a number of specific laws, since it belongs to systems with an established metasystem level. It has been proven that the leading role in the genesis of the motivational field is played by ontologically included metasystems - metasystems of the person, activity and social environment. All three metasystems are sources of not only positive but also negative motivation. Therefore, in the process of mastering educational activities, the entire process of formation of the individual's motivational sphere is aimed at forming the opposite unity of two opposite tendencies - positive and negative motivation.

The laws of the genesis of the motivational sphere of the individual are determined in the educational activity, they complement the laws of the general and specific genetic system. This is, in particular, the presence of a sensitive period in each of the main motivational subsystems; genetic relativity of many laws of organization of motivation field; includes such things as the existence of gender differences in the movement of motivational laws.

Many researchers conclude that the problem of motivation for educational activities is a part of the broader problem of motivation in a general psychological sense. It follows that all the categories, laws, contradictions and difficulties arising in the study of motivation in the general psychological sense are related to the motivation of educational activities in its study.

Studying the problem of motivation for educational activity in psychology, E.V. Karpova notes that the current situation of the problem of motivation for educational activity was influenced by a special direction related to the study of the characteristics of motivation for labor activity (W. Vroom, I. Yeton, E. Mayo, F. Taylor, A. Fayol, and others). These studies were both purely theoretical and practical in nature. This fact shows the clear advantage of learning one of the main

types of activity - work motivation, compared to the other two - education and play. E.V. Karpova cites the "theory of labor investments" as an example. According to him, the more effort a person puts into his work, that is, the more he "invests" in it, the more he attracts and motivates him, not only his results, but also satisfaction will also grow from it. The practical significance of this theory is of great importance. This also applies to the problem of motivation for educational activities that we are considering. It should be noted that E.V. The results of the research conducted by Karpova are the verification of the position that is important for the psychology of the motivation of educational activities, according to which the motivational field of the person in it is based on the structural-level principle and forms a hierarchy of a set of naturally organized levels.

In the process of ontogeny, the motivation of educational activities changes significantly, which is confirmed by already conducted studies (S.M. Biryukov, L.I. Bojovich, A.N. Bukina, N.O. Vikulova, E.L. Vinogradova, B.S. Volkov, E.B. Goncharova, A.K. Dusavitsky, N.E. Yelfimova, E.V. Karpova, L.V. Katkova, O.Yu. Leshenko, A.K. Markova, M.V. Matyukhina, N.I. Meshkov, T.N. Nezamaeva, K.T. Patrina, D.V. Soldatova, V.D. Shadrikov, D.B. Elkonin, A.E. Gottfried, J.S. Fleming, A.W. Gottfried, S.Harter, G. Heyman, C. Dweck, K. Cain, et al.).

In general, the following can be concluded. First, all major psychological theories were sources for understanding the causes of behavior and action, including learning; understanding the great complexity and polymotivation of the other.

Secondly, the necessary conditions for studying the motivation of educational activities existed primarily in behaviorism, as well as partially in humanistic and cognitive psychology.

Literary sources contain significantly fewer definitions of the concepts of "motivation to learn", "motivation for learning", "motivation of educational activity". Unlike general psychological debates, heated discussions on this issue are kept to a minimum. So, S.P. According to Manukyan, needs are not motivations for learning. One of the main characteristics of educational activity is the specificity of the need that the teacher responds to - "learning is aimed at satisfying cognitive needs".

Motives of educational activity mean all factors that determine the manifestation of educational activity: needs, goals, relationships, sense of duty, interests, etc. Learning activity motivation is a special type of motivation included in learning activities. Often this term is used as a synonym for the concept of "cognitive motivation".

A.K. According to Markova and her co-authors, "in teaching, the motivation is the orientation of students to particular aspects of the educational process. The most appropriate reason for educational activity is the orientation of schoolchildren to mastering new ways of action." Accordingly, these definitions refer mainly to the components, rather than to the dynamic understanding of the content of these concepts.

Such terminological underdevelopment in the field of motivation of educational activity, lack of integrated theoretical ideas on the problem of motivation of educational activity and the motivation of educational activity in the last ten years compared to the 80s of the XX century due to the lack of clear experimental-psychological studies. It was found that educational motivation has a very complex structure and has its own characteristics at each age stage.

It is important that it is still almost impossible to single out any special motivational formations as determinants of educational activity.

All these are general, "formative" motivational areas that are clearly "connected" to the field of educational activity. According to B. Weiner, educational motivation is a combination of integrity and systematicity of educational motives. Educational activities should be organized in such a way as to help maximize the internal motivational potential of the student [306]. M. O. Rezvantseva said that the definition of the term "educational motivation" is a difficult issue to study in terms of its

content and semantic meanings. This term can be considered both in a broad (social motivations for learning) and narrow (as motivations for teaching a specific subject) context."

The terms "instrumental" and "integrative" types of motivation are also used in scientific and educational literature on the psychology of motivation. For example, R. Gardner and V. Lambert use these terms when studying the motivation for learning a foreign language. Instrumental motivation, according to the authors, surrounds external needs - the student learns a foreign language for money, career, power, passing exams. Integral motivation reflects the student's personal desire to learn a foreign language. Basically, instrumental motivation is similar to extrinsic motivation and integrative motivation is similar to intrinsic motivation.

Discussion. In our opinion, it is legitimate to think that it is not enough to divide motives only into internal and external types. External motives themselves can be positive (success, achievement motives) and negative (avoidance, protection motives). So, A.R. In Mansurova's work, educational motivation includes various incentives - needs, motives, goals, ideals, interests, aspirations. "Learning motivation as a systematic education is related to a wider system - personal motivation". According to the author, the central component of educational motivation is educational and cognitive motivation, which involves directing students not only to knowledge, but also to methods of acquiring it.

To date, the idea that motivation in the general psychological concept is not only a complex, dynamic formation, but also the motivation of educational activity is a similar, no less complex organized formation.

The analysis of literary sources and the psychological analysis of educational activities showed that the characteristics of the motivation of this activity are combined into two main categories. These are the general characteristics that are typical for him and for the personality system as a whole; characteristics that are specific to the motivation of educational activities, but they are related to and depend on the general characteristics of the organization of the motivational system of a person. Therefore, the motivation of educational activity is a specific motivation in its general psychological concept, characterized by the complexity of its content and structure, and generally works as a systematic and very specific individual.

It seems necessary to analyze the conceptual apparatus of the psychology of motivation for educational activities, because it helps to review and describe in detail the results obtained so far. Briefly describing the conceptual apparatus used in the psychology of motivation in general and the motivation of educational activities in particular, we consider it necessary to dwell on the review of empirical and experimental studies of the motivation of educational activities. We mentioned above that the phenomenon of motivation has attracted the attention of researchers since ancient times. In the process of phylogenesis, it was noted that the point of view about the origin of motivation, including educational motivation, has changed several times and depends on the level of development of science in a certain historical period. As part of our work, without pretending to be a complete review of the ideas in chronological order, we will consider the most important ones that are directly related to the topic of study.

In this regard, V.D. Shadrikov's opinion that the loss of contact with the child's interests when introduced into the world of abstract scientific knowledge leads to the impossibility of forming the student as a subject of educational activity seems important. The first serious systematic experimental studies of the motivation of educational activities carried out in Russian psychology were carried out in the 40s of the last century by L.I. It focuses on the work done by Bojović and his students.

Studying the problem of the driving forces of the child's mental development, he rightly drew attention to the need for a purposeful study of the child's motivational-needs area. It was determined that the educational activity of schoolchildren is motivated by a system of various motives.

Depending on the age of the children, the characteristics of each child, the importance of certain motives and the driving force differ significantly. As L. I. Bojovich noted, "some of them are leading, main; others are secondary, secondary..." .

He also distinguished two large groups of motives. Motives related to the content of educational activity and the process of its implementation, and motives related to the broader relationship of the child with the outside world.

The separation of these two groups of motives was, in essence, the first of the currently available classifications of educational activity motives. An in-depth study of these categories of motivations for educational activity made it possible to determine that, firstly, these motivations are important for the effective implementation of not only educational activity, but also any other activity; secondly, the indicated two categories of educational activity motives have their own characteristics at different stages of children's development. P.M. Jacobson considered a very wide range of the psychology of motivation, including the motivation of educational activities. He distinguished three very different types of motivation for educational activities.

An important stage in the experimental study of the motivation of educational activity is associated with the beginning of the 70s of the last century, which is determined by the increase in research on this problem. During this period, a significant increase in work in the field of problem-based education was observed in pedagogical psychology, the theory of educational activity was intensively developed, and the theory of the gradual formation of mental actions was further developed. Therefore, it is natural for researchers to focus on the role and importance of motivation in relation to the directions being developed. Thus, V.N. Maksimova states that there is a multifaceted interaction between problem-based learning and cognitive interest, and that "the level of the student's cognitive interest determines the choice of the task, the activity of participation in solving it, and the nature of the motivation of cognitive activity. High cognitive interest means greater cognitive importance provides the choice of more complex tasks and the most effective effect of problem-based education on the mental development of the student" .

V.F. Morgun analyzed the motivational possibilities of various types of education from the point of view of the theory of P. Ya. Galperin. A. K. Dusavitsky studied the educational interests of elementary school students who mastered materials from linguistics and mathematics in the form of educational activities, the content of which is theoretical concepts of these subjects, and the presence of qualitatively new features of motivation in comparison with public school students. showed. It was also found that many students were interested in the methods of educational activities, and this direction of interest was characteristic of most students. We note that according to A.K. Markova, this happens much later in normal traditional educational conditions.

Educational activity is an important content of almost the entire period of personality development, from preparation for school and kindergarten to teaching in higher educational institutions. Education is an indispensable requirement of society for any person, so the problem of learning motivation becomes one of the main problems of psychology. In the process of education, the formation and development of individual psychological characteristics of a person takes place depending on the psychological structure of a certain activity, its direction, and the motives that motivate it.

Educational motivation allows a developing person to determine not only the direction, but also the methods of implementation of various forms of educational activity, to involve the emotional and volitional sphere. It serves as an important multifactorial determinant that determines the specific characteristics of the educational situation at each time interval.

The general name of the processes, methods and means of engaging students in effective knowledge activities and encouraging them to actively master the educational content is the concept of "educational motivation".->

Motivation for educational activity usually means all factors that determine the manifestation of educational activity - needs, goals, attitudes, sense of duty, interests, etc.→

Summary. So, motivation is determined by a number of factors: the nature of the educational system, the organization of the pedagogical process, the personal characteristics of the teacher, the specific characteristics of the subject, the specific characteristics of the student (gender, age, mastery level, intellectual development and abilities, value orientation, self-esteem, etc.).

Motivation as a process of changing a person's situations and attitudes is based on motives, which are understood as specific motives, reasons that force a person to perform actions and actions. The role of motives is interconnected between needs and interests, aspirations and feelings, attitudes and ideals. Therefore, motives are very complex formations, in which there are dynamic systems in which alternative options are analyzed and evaluated, choices are made and decisions are made.

In short, in psychology, the identification of different levels and forms of personality is accompanied by the recognition of the important role of the structures responsible for the activation of mental and activity manifestations. Such psychological formations include phenomena described in psychology by the concepts of "needs", "personal orientation", "motivational sphere" and others. They allow you to give meaning to life events and build them according to the line of a person's life path.

The review of scientific and literary sources allowed us to conclude that the problem of developing the student's learning motivation under the influence of values has not yet been sufficiently studied for effective use in solving personal development problems.

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